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PROBLEMS OF FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL PEDAGOGY

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ABSTRACT

A modern teacher must be well-versed in the various branches of science whose foundations they teach and understand its potential for solving socio-economic, industrial, and cultural problems. But this is not enough – they must constantly be abreast of new research, discoveries, and hypotheses, and perceive the immediate and distant prospects of the science they teach. The most general characteristic of a teacher's cognitive orientation is a culture of scientific and pedagogical thinking, the main feature of which is dialecticism. This is manifested in the ability to detect the contradictions that comprise every pedagogical phenomenon. A dialectical view of pedagogical phenomena allows teachers to perceive it as a process in which continuous development occurs through the struggle between the new and the old, and to influence this process by promptly resolving all issues and problems that arise in their work.

Keywords: Personal and pedagogical values, ideological characteristics of a teacher's personality, pedagogy, psychology, education.

PROFESSIONAL PEDAGOGIKANING SHAKLLANISHI VA RIVOJLANISHI MUAMMOLARI

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ANNOTATSIYA

Zamonaviy o'qituvchi o'zi o'rgatadigan fanning turli sohalarini yaxshi bilishi va uning ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, sanoat va madaniy muammolarni hal qilishdagi salohiyatini tushunishi kerak. Ammo bu yetarli emas - ular doimo yangi tadqiqotlar, kashfiyotlar va gipotezalardan xabardor bo'lishlari va o'qitadigan fanning yaqin va uzoq istiqbollari idrok etishlari kerak. O'qituvchining kognitiv yo'nalishi eng umumiy xususiyat - bu ilmiy va pedagogik fikrlash madaniyati bo'lib, uning asosiy xususiyati dialektikadir. Bu har bir pedagogik hodisani tashkil etuvchi qarama-qarshiliklarni aniqlash qobiliyatida namoyon bo'ladi. Pedagogik hodisalarga dialektik qarash o'qituvchilarga uni yangi va eski o'rtasidagi kurash orqali uzluksiz rivojlanish sodir bo'ladigan jarayon sifatida idrok etish va o'z ishlarida yuzaga keladigan barcha masala va muammolarni tezda hal qilish orqali bu jarayonga ta'sir ko'rsatish imkonini beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Shaxsiy va pedagogik qadriyatlar, o'qituvchi shaxsining mafkuraviy xususiyatlari, pedagogika, psixologiya, ta'lim.

The Structure of Pedagogical Activity. Unlike the accepted understanding of activity in psychology as a multi-level system whose components include goals, motives, actions, and results, the prevailing approach to pedagogical activity is to distinguish its components as relatively independent functional types of teacher activity. N.V. Kuzmina identified three interrelated components in the structure of pedagogical activity: constructive, organizational, and communicative.

The successful implementation of these functional types of pedagogical activity requires the corresponding abilities, manifested in skills. Constructive activity, in turn, is divided into constructive-substantive (selection and composition of educational material, planning and constructing the pedagogical process), constructive-operational (planning one's own actions and those of students), and constructive-material (designing the educational and material base of the pedagogical process).

Organizational activity involves implementing a system of actions aimed at engaging students in various activities, creating a team, and organizing joint activities.

Communicative activity is aimed at establishing pedagogically appropriate relationships between the teacher and students, other school teachers, community representatives, and parents. However, these components, on the one hand, can equally be attributed not only to pedagogical activity but to almost any other activity, while on the other, they do not sufficiently cover all aspects and areas of pedagogical activity. A.I. Shcherbakov classifies constructive, organizational, and research components (functions) as general labor functions, i.e., they are manifested in any activity[1].

However, he concretizes the teacher's function at the stage of implementing the pedagogical process, presenting the organizational component of pedagogical activity as a unity of informational, developmental, orientational, and mobilization functions. Particular attention should be paid to the research function, although it is related to general work functions. Implementing the research function requires teachers to adopt a scientific approach to pedagogical phenomena, master heuristic search skills, and employ methods of scientific and pedagogical research, including analysis of their own experience and that of other teachers. The constructive component of pedagogical activity can be represented as internally interconnected analytical, prognostic, and projective functions. All components, or functional types of activity, are manifested in the work of a teacher of any specialty. Their implementation presupposes the possession of specialized skills by the teacher.

One of the most important requirements of the teaching profession is a clear social and professional position for its members. It is through this position that teachers express themselves as subjects of pedagogical activity. A teacher's position is a system of intellectual, volitional, and emotionally evaluative attitudes toward the world, pedagogical reality, and pedagogical activity in particular, which are the source of their activity. It is determined, on the one hand, by the demands, expectations, and opportunities presented and provided by society, and on the other, by internal, personal sources of activity—the teacher's drives, experiences, motives, and goals, their value orientations, worldview, and ideals. A teacher's position reflects their personality, the nature of their social orientation, and their type of civic behavior and activity. A

teacher's social position grows out of the system of views, beliefs, and value orientations formed in comprehensive school[2].

During professional training, these foundations form a motivational and value-based approach to the teaching profession, the goals, and means of teaching. This motivational and value-based approach to teaching, in its broadest sense, ultimately manifests itself in a focus that forms the core of a teacher's personality.

A teacher's social position largely determines their professional position. However, there is no direct correlation, as education is always built on the foundation of personal interaction. This is why a teacher, while clearly understanding their actions, is often unable to provide a detailed explanation of why they act the way they do, often contrary to common sense and logic. No analysis can reveal which sources of motivation prevailed when a teacher chose a particular position in a given situation if they attribute their decision to intuition. Many factors influence a teacher's choice of professional position.

However, the decisive ones among them are his professional attitudes, individual typological features of personality, temperament and character. L. B. Itelson gave the characteristics of typical role pedagogical positions. The teacher can act as: an informant, if he limits himself to communicating requirements, norms, views, etc. (for example, one must be honest); a friend, if he strives to penetrate into the soul of the child; a dictator, if he forcibly introduces norms and value orientations into the consciousness of the pupils; an advisor, if he uses careful persuasion; a petitioner, if he begs the pupil to be like this, "as it should be", sometimes stooping to self-abasement, flattery; an inspirer, if he strives to captivate (ignite) the pupils with interesting goals, prospects. Each of these positions can give a positive and negative effect depending on the personality of the educator. However, injustice and arbitrariness always give negative results; playing along with the child, turning him into a little idol and dictator; bribery, disrespect for the child's personality, suppression of his initiative, etc.

The totality of professionally determined requirements for a teacher is defined as professional readiness for teaching. It legitimately includes psychological,

psychophysiological, and physical readiness, on the one hand, and scientific, theoretical, and practical competence as the foundation of professionalism, on the other. The content of professional readiness, as a reflection of the goal of pedagogical education, is summarized in a job description, which reflects the invariant, idealized parameters of the teacher's personality and professional activity. To date, extensive experience has been accumulated in constructing a teacher job description, which allows professional requirements for a teacher to be combined into three main, interconnected and complementary sets: general civic qualities;

Qualities that define the specifics of the teaching profession; specialized knowledge, abilities, and skills in the subject (specialty). When substantiating a job description, psychologists rely on establishing a list of pedagogical abilities, which represent a synthesis of the qualities of the mind, feelings, and will of the individual. In particular, V. A. Krutetsky identifies didactic, academic, and communicative abilities, as well as pedagogical imagination and the ability to distribute attention. A. I. Shcherbakov includes didactic, constructive, perceptual, expressive, communicative, and organizational abilities among the most important pedagogical abilities[3].

He also believes that a teacher's psychological makeup should include general civic qualities, moral-psychological, social-perceptual, individual-psychological characteristics, and practical skills: general pedagogical (informational, mobilizing, developmental, and orientational), general work skills (constructive, organizational, and research), communicative (communication with people of all ages), and self-educational (systematization and generalization of knowledge and its application in solving pedagogical problems and acquiring new information). A teacher is not just a profession whose essence is to transmit knowledge, but a lofty mission of creating personality, affirming the individual within.

In this regard, the goal of pedagogical education can be represented as the continuous general and professional development of a new type of teacher, characterized by: high civic responsibility and social activity; love for children, the need and ability to give them their heart; genuine intelligence, spiritual culture, the

desire and ability to work collaboratively; high professionalism, an innovative style of scientific and pedagogical thinking, a willingness to create new values and make creative decisions; the need for and readiness for continuous self-education; physical and mental health, and professional performance. This succinct and concise characterization of a teacher can be further specified down to the level of personal characteristics. In a teacher's job description, the leading place is occupied by their personality orientation.

In this regard, let us consider the personal qualities of a teacher-educator, characterizing his/her social-moral, professional-pedagogical, and cognitive orientation. K. D. Ushinsky wrote: "The most important path of human education is conviction, and conviction can only be influenced by conviction. Any teaching program, any educational method, no matter how good it may be, that is not translated into the educator's convictions, will remain a dead letter, having no force in reality. The most vigilant control will not help in this matter. An educator can never be a blind executor of instructions: not warmed by the warmth of his/her personal conviction, it will have no power" [8].

In a teacher's work, ideological conviction defines all other personality traits and characteristics that express their social and moral orientation, including social needs, moral and value orientations, and a sense of public duty and civic responsibility. Ideological conviction underlies a teacher's social engagement. For this reason, it is rightfully considered the most profound and fundamental characteristic of a teacher's personality. A teacher-citizen is loyal to their people and close to them. They do not isolate themselves within the narrow circle of their personal concerns; their life is continuously connected with the life of the village and city where they live and work.

A teacher's professional-pedagogical orientation plays a special role in their personality structure. It serves as the framework around which the key professionally significant personality traits of a teacher are assembled. A teacher's professional orientation encompasses an interest in the teaching profession, a pedagogical calling, and professional-pedagogical intentions and inclinations. The foundation of a teacher's

pedagogical orientation is an interest in the teaching profession, which is expressed in a positive emotional attitude toward children, parents, teaching in general and in specific types of teaching, and a desire to master pedagogical knowledge and skills.

A vocation for teaching, unlike a pedagogical interest, which can be speculative, signifies an inclination that stems from a recognition of one's aptitude for teaching. The presence or absence of a vocation can only be revealed through the future teacher's involvement in academic or professionally oriented activities, as a person's professional destiny is not directly and unambiguously determined by their unique natural abilities. Meanwhile, a subjective experience of a calling for a current or even chosen activity can prove to be a highly significant factor in personal development, engendering a passion for the activity and a conviction of one's suitability for it. Thus, a vocation for teaching develops as a future teacher accumulates theoretical and practical teaching experience and self-assesses their teaching abilities. This suggests that deficiencies in specialized (academic) preparation cannot serve as grounds for declaring a future teacher's complete professional unsuitability. The foundation of a vocation for teaching lies in a love for children[5].

This fundamental quality is a prerequisite for self-improvement and the purposeful development of many professionally significant qualities that characterize a teacher's professional and pedagogical focus. Among these qualities are pedagogical duty and responsibility. Guided by a sense of pedagogical duty, teachers always strive to provide assistance to children and adults, to all who need it, within the limits of their rights and competence. They are demanding of themselves, strictly adhering to a unique code of pedagogical ethics. The highest manifestation of pedagogical duty is a teacher's dedication. It is in this dedication that their motivational and value-based approach to work is expressed. A teacher possessing this quality works without regard for time, sometimes even for their health. The life and work of A.S. Makarenko and V.A. Sukhomlinsky are striking examples of professional dedication.

An exceptional example of selflessness and sacrifice is the life and heroism of Janusz Korczak, a prominent Polish physician and educator who defied the Nazis' offer

to let him live and stepped into the crematorium oven with his students. A teacher's relationships with colleagues, parents, and children, based on a sense of professional duty and responsibility, constitute the essence of pedagogical tact, which is simultaneously a sense of proportion, a conscious dosage of action, and the ability to control it and, if necessary, balance one means with another. A teacher's tactic, in any case, consists of anticipating its consequences, choosing the appropriate style and tone, time, and place of pedagogical action, and making timely adjustments[4].

Pedagogical tact depends largely on the teacher's personal qualities, their outlook, culture, will, civic position, and professional skills. It is the foundation upon which trusting relationships between teachers and students are nurtured. Pedagogical tact is particularly evident in the teacher's assessment and control activities, where particular attentiveness and fairness are crucial. Pedagogical fairness represents a unique measure of a teacher's objectivity and level of moral upbringing. V. A. Sukhomlinsky wrote: "Fairness is the basis of a child's trust in their teacher. But there is no abstract justice—one that transcends individuality, personal interests, passions, and impulses. To be fair, one must thoroughly understand the spiritual world of each child" [9].

The personal qualities that characterize a teacher's professional and pedagogical focus are the prerequisite and concentrated expression of their authority. While other professions commonly use terms like "scientific authority," "recognized authority in their field," and the like, a teacher can possess a single, indivisible personal authority. The foundation of a person's cognitive focus is formed by spiritual needs and interests. One of the manifestations of spiritual strength and cultural needs is the need for knowledge. Continuous pedagogical self-education is a necessary condition for professional development and improvement. One of the main factors of cognitive interest is a love for the subject being taught.

L. N. Tolstoy noted that if "you want to educate a student through science, love your science and know it, and the students will love you, and you will educate them; but if you yourself do not love it, then no matter how much you force them to study, science will not produce an educational influence" [1]. This idea was also developed

by V. A. Sukhomlinsky. He believed that "a master of pedagogy knows the ABCs of his science so well that in the lesson, during the study of the material, the center of his attention is not the content of what is being studied, but the students, their mental work, their thinking, the difficulties of their mental work" [9].

To understand the essence of professional and pedagogical culture, it is necessary to keep in mind the following provisions that reveal the connection between general and professional culture, its specific features: • professional and pedagogical culture is a universal characteristic of pedagogical reality, manifested in different forms of existence; • professional and pedagogical culture is an internalized general culture and performs the function of specific projection of general culture into the sphere of pedagogical activity; • professional and pedagogical culture is a systemic formation that includes a number of structural and functional components, has its own organization, selectively interacts with the environment and possesses the integrative property of the whole, not reducible to the properties of individual parts; • the unit of analysis of professional and pedagogical culture is pedagogical activity, creative in nature; • the peculiarities of the implementation and formation of the professional and pedagogical culture of a teacher are determined by individual creative, psychophysiological and age characteristics, the established social and pedagogical experience of the individual. Taking into account the specified methodological foundations makes it possible to substantiate a model of professional and pedagogical culture, the constituent components of which are axiological, technological and personal-creative. The axiological component of professional and pedagogical culture is formed by a set of pedagogical values created by humanity and originally included in the integral pedagogical process at the current stage of educational development.

In the process of teaching, teachers master ideas and concepts, acquiring knowledge and skills that constitute the humanistic technology of teaching. Depending on the degree of their application in real life, they evaluate these as more significant. Knowledge, ideas, and concepts that currently hold great significance for society and a particular educational system act as pedagogical values. Teachers become masters of

their craft, professionals, as they master and develop their teaching practice, recognizing pedagogical values. The history of school and pedagogical thought is a process of constant evaluation, rethinking, establishing values, and transferring known ideas and pedagogical technologies to new contexts. The ability to recognize something new in something well-known and to appreciate it is an essential component of a teacher's pedagogical culture. The technological component of professional pedagogical culture includes the methods and techniques of a teacher's pedagogical activity. The values and achievements of pedagogical culture are mastered and created by the individual through activity, confirming the inextricable link between culture and activity. The humanistic focus of pedagogical activity makes it possible to explore the mechanism for satisfying the diverse spiritual needs of the individual. In particular, how and in what way are the needs for communication, for acquiring new information, for sharing accumulated individual experience satisfied—that is, everything that underlies the holistic educational process—met[6].

Pedagogical activity is inherently technological. Therefore, an operational analysis of pedagogical activity is required, allowing us to view it as a solution to a variety of pedagogical problems. These include a combination of analytical-reflexive, constructive-prognostic, organizational-activity, evaluative-informational, and corrective-regulatory tasks, the methods and techniques for solving which constitute the technology of a teacher's professional-pedagogical culture. Pedagogical technology helps us understand the essence of pedagogical culture; it reveals historically changing methods and techniques, explaining the direction of activity depending on the evolving relations in society. It is in this context that pedagogical culture functions as a regulator, preserver, reproducer, and developer of pedagogical reality. The personal-creative component of professional-pedagogical culture reveals the mechanism for mastering it and implementing it as a creative act. The process of teacher appropriation of the pedagogical values developed occurs at the personal-creative level[10].

By mastering the values of pedagogical culture, teachers are able to transform and interpret them, which is determined both by their personal characteristics and the nature of their teaching. It is in teaching that the contradictions of creative self-realization are discovered and resolved, as well as the fundamental contradiction between the accumulated pedagogical experience of society and the specific forms of its individual creative appropriation and development, the contradiction between the level of development of the individual's strengths and abilities and the self-denial and overcoming of this development, and so on. Thus, pedagogical creativity is a form of human activity, the universal characteristic of which is pedagogical culture.

Pedagogical creativity requires teachers to meet their needs, possess specific abilities, demonstrate individual freedom, independence, and responsibility. It becomes clear that pedagogical culture is the sphere of creative application and realization of a teacher's pedagogical abilities. Through pedagogical values, the individual objectifies their individual strengths and mediates the process of appropriating moral, aesthetic, legal, and other relationships. In other words, by influencing others, the individual creates themselves, determines their own development, and realizes their potential through activity. An analysis of philosophical, historical-pedagogical, and psychological-pedagogical literature, a study of the experiences of school teachers, and theoretical generalizations allow us to conclude that professional-pedagogical culture is a measure and method of creative self-realization for the teacher in various forms of pedagogical activity and communication aimed at mastering and creating pedagogical values and technologies. The presented understanding of professional-pedagogical culture allows us to incorporate this concept into a categorical series: the culture of pedagogical activity, the culture of pedagogical communication, and the teacher's personal culture. Professional and pedagogical culture represents a universal characteristic of various types of teacher activity and pedagogical communication, revealing and supporting the development of needs, interests, value orientations, and individual abilities related to pedagogical activity and pedagogical communication. Professional and pedagogical culture is a concept at a

higher level of abstraction, concretized in the concepts of "culture of pedagogical activity," "culture of pedagogical communication," and "teacher's personal culture."

Pedagogical values are objective, as they are formed historically through the development of society, education, and the general education system, and are captured in pedagogical science as a form of social consciousness in the form of specific images and concepts. In the process of preparing for and implementing pedagogical activity, teachers master pedagogical values and subjectify them. The level of subjectification of pedagogical values is an indicator of the teacher's personal and professional development, their pedagogical culture as the degree to which they realize ideal values, transforming the potential (ought) into the actual (existent). As the conditions of social and pedagogical life change, and the needs of society, the school, and the individual evolve, pedagogical values also change and are re-evaluated. However, they serve as relatively stable guidelines by which teachers align their lives and teaching activities.

The integration of universal human values of goodness and beauty, justice and duty, equality and honor into a palette of pedagogical values, their mastery, and the deepening of the world of pedagogical values create the material foundation upon which the edifice of a teacher's professional and pedagogical culture is built. A teacher's subjective perception and appropriation of universal cultural and pedagogical values is determined by the richness of their personality, the focus of their professional activity, their professional and pedagogical self-awareness, and their personal pedagogical system, thus reflecting their inner world. In this regard, S. L. Rubinstein's assertion that value attitudes remain a means of reflecting reality in the human consciousness is correct. The degree to which an individual assimilates pedagogical values depends on the state of their pedagogical consciousness, since the establishment of the value of a given pedagogical idea or pedagogical phenomenon occurs through the process of its individual evaluation. The criterion for the evaluation and its outcome is a generalized image formed on the basis of psychological and pedagogical knowledge, the results of one's own activities, and a comparison with the activities of others. The images of individual pedagogical consciousness may or may not coincide

with the ideas developed in society or a professional group about the goals, content, subject and object of pedagogical activity, about everything that ensures pedagogical competence and the appropriateness of the teacher's activities[7].

A teacher's professional and pedagogical consciousness performs a complex regulatory function. It structures the entire diversity of acquired and implemented methods of educational, upbringing, methodological, and social-pedagogical activity around a single personal core. A. N. Leontyev notes that the subject's diverse activities intersect and are connected into nodes by the objective, inherently social relationships into which they necessarily enter. These nodes, in his opinion, form the "decoration of the personality" that we call the "I." The hierarchy of teacher activities stimulates the development of individuality. The teacher accumulates this diversity, being at the center of a uniquely structured and organized activity. In the process of their work, each teacher, as an individual, actualizes only that portion of their professional and pedagogical values that is vital and professionally necessary for them.

This characteristic of essential professional initiative is imbued in the teacher's consciousness in the form of the "professional self," which informs their individualized professional-pedagogical experience and associated experiences, beliefs, professional connections, and relationships. Professional consciousness is aimed at analyzing various aspects of the teacher's self and their professional activity and is intended to define the boundaries and perspectives of personal meaning, i.e., the internally motivated, individual significance of a given action or deed for the subject. It allows the teacher to self-define and self-actualize, ultimately addressing the question of the meaning of life. Representing not only a system of the most general judgments and knowledge about activity, oneself, others, and society, pedagogical consciousness is also the product and result of exclusively individual experience, a special mechanism for the professional development of the teacher's personality, allowing the universality of pedagogical culture to become an individual sphere of activity[6].

Pedagogical values, being the condition and result of corresponding activity, have different levels of existence: individual-personal, professional-group, and socio-

pedagogical. Socio-pedagogical values reflect the nature and content of values operating in various social systems, manifesting themselves in the public consciousness in the form of morality, religion, and philosophy. They are a set of ideas, norms, and rules regulating society's activities in the field of education. Group pedagogical values represent a set of ideas, concepts, and norms regulating and guiding pedagogical activity within specific educational institutions. The set of such values is holistic in nature and acts as a cognitive-active system, possessing relative stability and repeatability. These values serve as guidelines for pedagogical activity in certain professional groups (school, lyceum, and gymnasium teachers; college, technical school, and university instructors).

Personal and pedagogical values are complex socio-psychological constructs that reflect the goals, motives, ideals, attitudes, and other ideological characteristics of a teacher's personality, constituting their system of value orientations. The latter, representing the axiological self, is given to the individual not as a system of knowledge, but as a system of cognitive formations associated with emotional and volitional components, accepted by the individual as an internal guide, motivating and guiding their activities. The consciousness of each individual teacher, accumulating socio-pedagogical and professional-group values, builds their own personal value system, the elements of which take the form of axiological functions. Such functions may include the concept of developing the personality of a specialist, the concept of activity, ideas about the technology of organizing the educational process in school, the specifics of interaction with students, their concept of themselves as a professional, etc. The integrative axiological function, uniting all others, is the individual's concept of the meaning of professional and pedagogical activity in the life of a teacher.

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